

Work Life Balance and Time Management – A Case Study with Reference to Yenepoya Speciality Hospital Kodialbail, Mangalore

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays work life balance is becoming a rapidly growing concern for both employees and the employers, this topic basically deals with employees ability to properly prioritize and balance between their work and family, social life, lifestyle etc which is connected with the employees productivity. Because of continuous work time schedules in the hospital sometimes managing time and work pressure becomes difficult for the employees due to which they may not get enough time for their personal life to balance with their work life which will affect the growth and expansion of the hospital in an indirect or direct way. For the growth and expansion of any industry the contribution of its employees with full head and heart is very essential. If the industry needs its employees to work with them for longer period of time it's the responsibility of the industry to fulfill the job needs and provide them assistance wherever needed which will boost their morale and motivate them to be the part of any particular industry for longer period of

time and it will also give them motivation and interest to serve for the industry since they are highly satisfied with their job procedures and also the norms and rules of the industry.

Key Words: Work life, Employees Expectation, Working Environment, Industry policy.

INTRODUCTION

This topic had been selected in order to know how the hospital undertakes and maintains supportive, healthy and flexible working environment that will help the employees of the hospital to have a balance between their work and the personal responsibilities and which may also enable to strengthen the loyalty and productivity of the employees towards their work and their contribution to the overall growth and expansion of the industry which is one of the most common and essential factors of any organization.

Now a days in global perspective, organizations compete with each other. They try to get such advantages which cannot be attained and achieved easily by other organizations. In order to get some competitive advantages, they use different techniques and try to satisfy their employees. There are three dependent and independent variables. Dependent variable is work life balance. Independent variables are Absenteeism and Time management.

Work-Life balance refers to an effective management or striking a balance between the work which is remunerated and the personal or social responsibilities which an individual is expected to perform. Work life can influence organizational productivity and also the well-being of the employees in different ways.

To study the current work life balance and time management policies that the hospital is following and to suggest what extra procedures can be added for this policy for the betterment of employees and to understand what is the perception of employees regarding the work life balance and to know what is work life balance according to them and how it should be applied by the hospital

Company profile

Yenepoya Specialty Hospital had started by the visionary leader, the late Mr Yenepoya Moideen Kunhi, that has the span of over half a century which is grown into a robust conglomerate- The Yenepoya Group. Overall the hospital consists of two branches one in kodial bail and another in

deralakatte.

The hospital was started with a small building with few employees and with less facilities, with the constant effort and strategies they were able to achieve as well as expand their business, over a particular period they become one of the leading competitors for other hospitals within the city, YENEPOYA SPECIALTY HOSPITAL, one of the ventures by the yenepoya group, which is located in the heart of Mangalore city established in the year 1995 has an built up area of more than 150000/- sq.ft with spacious common areas and well laid out rooms with good ambience.

Yenepoya Specialty Hospital a tertiary care unit with a capacity of 234 beds, that include 30-40 critical beds and multiple Specialties which include Interventional cardiology, cardiothoracic Surgery, Orthopedics and Joint Replacement, Urology, cancer care, Spine Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynecology and NIU, Rheumatology, ENT, Nephrology, Surgical Specialties, Internal Medicine, Dental, Dermatology, Ophthalmology, Pediatrics, Intensive care units, Anesthesiology, Accident and Emergency Centre etc.

With the new and latest technology infrastructure, multitude of specialty care units and a highly proficient medical care team, they boast themselves as one among the best in the industry, also their highly qualified medical professionals team and healthcare management team are available and ready to help round the clock also the rooms are available at different rates and have a unchanging mark of quality, comfort and convenience various measures are taken to maintain patient privacy by allowing patients benefiting them by economic tariffs and making some amenities such as dedicated wardrobe, television, air conditioning that are available at varied range based on our requirements.

VISION: “To be the most trusted Hospital in the region”.

MISSION: “To create an ecosystem wherein Healthcare is dispensed in an ethical way by a passionate skilled clinical team.

Theoretical background of the study

Work life balance can be referred as the balance between the time given for work and after work the time spent for other personal life factors which is necessary for an individual who is working in any firm. The term work life balance consist of categorizing the two factors the work life and personal life as an employee’s priority so that he can be proved as responsible by equally

managing and balancing both factors efficiently and also through which the employees can lead a stress free life without any pressure from both the factors.

Work life balance is an option and initiative that every employee should opt for, Most importantly it is the responsibility of the firm to take a step forward and provide assistance to its employees in today's era almost every employees are not only in search of jobs but also they expect the organization to show some care in terms of giving facilities at work place where the employees can feel that they are not under continues work burden and they are given the work timings in such a way that they are able to spend the required and quality time with the family, If any company is successful in fulfilling these needs of the employees it can lead to employee retention, which can give employees the chance of career growth expansion and better opportunities and also this will lead to job satisfaction which will result in reduction of employees mental and physical stress.

Most of the companies are introducing innovative and unique policies through which their employees an get enough time to spend with family and enjoy, Nowadays it has become a trend and necessity for the firms to maintain and continue proper work life balance policies and practices that can help to inculcate various elements like employees loyalty, dedication and commitment towards the work, reduced rate of employee turnover, improved performance by industry ,growth in employee morale and reduced absenteeism due to satisfaction of the employees and reduction in turnover rates.

By adopting essential terms and policies in any company it will help to support and motivate healthy and effective work life balance which will benefit and can be an advantage to both the employees as well as the organization.

In personal life satisfaction of employees and their capabilities to reach personal goals influence the success as an employee, which is highly beneficial for any firm. Work satisfaction, peace of mind and achieving longer career in a company can be attained by helping employees to maintain good work life balance, organization that helps in building and planning the policies to publicize more work life balance will not only analyze the expansion and efficient productivity but also observe employee retention and decreased cost pertaining to growing turnover.

Improper balance between work and personal life can have negative impact not only on

employees but also on the firm it will also increase the stress level which will result in poor productivity there will be high chances of health related issues and absenteeism this can also effect the relationship between the management and employees and also their personal relationship

The various advantages of work life balance are as follows:

- Stable employee health and improved well-being
- Helps to boost and increase competitiveness
- Change in perception of employees towards their work
- Lower stress and a healthy workforce team
- Helps to meet customer demands and expectations by reacting more effectively towards the flexible conditions of the market
- Minimization in turnover of employees and reduction in cost of recruitment
- If there is implementation of effective work life balance policy the organization can become well known and recognized by which it can attract capable manpower required and also people will get interested to work in such company
- Increases employee motivation and commitment

Work life balance consist of capability of an employee to manage a balance between the work roles, personal commitments and family responsibility so the firms are becoming aware and knowing the need of providing help to the employees to attain the stability of balance as many employees are going through the dispute of their work and personal roles.

In today's generation employees are seeing tremendous increase in their responsibility towards child and elderly care because almost many of them are highly educated and are independent enough to work irrespective of men women therefore to complete work commitments and Volunteer family there will be mismatch between personal and work roles that may lead to stress and depression.

Many ways are there in which firms assist to undertake work life balance procedures for their employees it also sees to it that the top level managers help in encouraging the them so that they could make optimum utilization of the procedures for their welfare by providing flexible and suitable work times, work choices depending on that employees can fix their working patterns so

that they can parallelly plan for their personal responsibilities which will help to reduce work and personal mismatch. Flexible working patterns or choices may consist of assigning work that can be done from home make use of job sharing technique, remote work, compressed working weeks, the management should motivate workers to make full use of the available leaves as per the procedures of the company.

The top level management should also motivate the employees for setting boundaries for work related mails and calls during non-working hours by not giving any response to it and many organizations are conducting different wellness programs that contains stress reduction workshop, time management programs, wellness centres on work site, help the staff to get in touch with mental health counselors, physicians and enabling gyms. As most of the companies are moving to globalization and adapting the modern times technology work is no longer stagnant in workplace itself staff can work from any corner of the world with utilization of internet, smart phones, online workings, telecommunication etc.

Literature Review

Beauregard and Henry (2009) stated that numerous organizations are paying significant attention to provide work –life balance practices, they are attracting worker to themselves and are enriching their employees' performance.

Murphy and Doherty (2011) Uncovered and it is strange to expect to quantify work-life balance in a flat out manner as there are close to home conditions which impact the manner in which it is seen yet building up a image that mirrors a person's needs though representatives must draw a firm line between their home and work lives and be certain that the line is in the perfect spot."

Scott (2011) stated that the use and understanding of time based structures is an important component for good individual time management include planning, meeting deadlines, sensing a lack of time control and engaging in procrastination.

Alsarayreh (2012) stated that Organizations must have more interest in time because of it is a scarce resource and it involves the various resources of the organization, if time was not managed, nothing else will be managed. And a good management of time is useful in providing the resources and the costs of the organization.

Pandita and singal (2017) investigated the relationship between employee engagement in fast changing environment is difficult without providing them work-life balance in terms of flexible timing, leave policy, compensation etc.. Thus the role of HR has increased to engage its employees strategically in this changing business paradigm to compete and sustain in market.

Alerge and Pasamar (2018) gave a new approach and benefits of work life balance which focuses of innovativeness. It also suggested that organizations should provide its employees with motivation, engagement and connecting creativity at workplace.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify how the employees are balancing their work life and personal life depending on the work procedures of the hospital by which they can obtain the Quality of Work life.
2. To understand about the working hour schedule of the employees in the hospital
3. To identify whether the employees get enough time to spend with their family after work.
4. To analyze that if employees have proper work life balance will the hospital be more successful.
5. To elicit the major impact of quality f work life on time management.

Scope of the study

The study was undertaken to measure and analyse several factors of work life balance and time management policy.

Management followed by the hospital and improve various needs like accountability, productivity, commitment for working better in teams, lower the negative organizational pressure and boost morale.

Research methodology

Secondary data: Secondary data are those which have been already collected before by researchers and which have already passed through the statistical process. Secondary data may either be published data or unpublished data. For the study the data was collected through referring the following:

- Articles and journals of the hospital.
- Textbooks
- Internet.

Limitation of the study: As always time is the limiting factor; this study suffers from time constraint.

Discussions of the study

Work life balance is a most important factor among employees. This is because lack of work life balance practice causes the employees' satisfaction. The main motive of this study was to check that what factors can determine the work life balance.

If the employee rate is less in company, work life balance can be achieved here. Time management practices determine the work life balance. Time management also plays a major role; if a time management is being practiced in hospitals then work life balance can be achieved smoothly.

Clear performance are discussed and established as a part of the flexible working arrangement. It should follow the process of job sharing which many large organizations follow a work assigned must be shared among all the employees simultaneously so that target would be reached within the given period of time through which the work pressure will be less for the employees and the productivity will also be effective.

Suggestions

The hospital should conduct wellness programs like stress management workshop, mental health awareness programs, counseling for better health and peace of mind and also undertake these activities practically like yoga and some mental and physical exercise sessions in between their working hours once in a month so that employees should feel burden free and relaxed this will help them to concentrate more on work, they will remain cheerful, active throughout the day and it will create positive environment for them

Recruitment and hiring must be done on frequent basis if there are shortage of employees, the existing employees should not be over pressured by assigning them work of non-existing employee but the employees should be hired and placed at right place and at right time whenever there is a need to do so without hindering the work schedule of other employees

Conclusion

Work life balance is about maintaining and stabilizing a balance between work achievements and personal enjoyments, it is very much crucial to practice positive work life balance for efficient

implementation of productivity that influence wellness of the staffs and also the hospital. It is the concept that elaborates about having accurate balance between the personal needs and other requirements of the individual and time allocated for work. The study reveals that the current work life balance management of the employees at Yenepoya Specialty Hospital is executed as per the plan of the hospital management, board members and HR team. They believe that the work life balance is well planned and effective in this hospital. If the hospital considers opinions and suggestions given by its employees it might help them to conduct practice of effective work life balance management.

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